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Relationship between Social Class and Parental Support on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the relationship between social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Student in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The Correlational research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and objectives guided the study with three hypotheses formulated for the study. The population of the study comprised students of Senior Secondary School class 2 in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. Record available from Rivers State Senior Secondary Schools board revealed that there are 11205 students, out of which 4603 are male and 6352 are female. The sample size of the study were 356 which was determined using Taro Yemen formula distribution and was used for the study. The simple random techniques was used to select students of Senior Secondary School class 2 in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The instrument for data collection is questionnaire on social lass (QSC) and Parental Support Academic Performance (PSAP) were determined by experts in measurements evaluation. The experts scrutinized the instruments in terms of quality, relevance and appropriateness of the items. The four point likerts scale was used for the study. The internal consistency reliability coefficients of the instruments used for data collection for the study were estimated using the Cronbach Alpha method. The reliability index was 0.75 and 0.82. The data collected for the study were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant level. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between social class and parental support on academic performances

Keywords: Social Class, Parental Support, Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

The importance of education in the development of both individual and community cannot be down played. Education is a process by which the mind of human beings develops through learning at human, street, religious institutions like churches, mosque, schools, colleges and ministries. It is also a process whereby a person develops attitudes and abilities that are considered to have value and relevance in the society. It is the best legacy a nation can give to her citizens especially the youth. Yusuf and Banawi (2020) opined that education must be considered as a key investment in modern economics because is previously seen within the framework of knowledge-based economy. There are strong and positive correlation between economic activity and education, in explaining economic growth. Asuru (2014) stated that education is a catalyst to the development of individuals in the society and nations as a whole. Dagbo (2014) opined that education is an important tool for social growth, development and interaction of all elements in the society.

Olayanju (2014) posited that education play sacrificial role in human capacity building and skill acquisition. Education cannot be restricted to the four corners of the school environment truly as it also outspread to the expansion of the home and experiences. School learning in context is a combined work of the school and the home environment which individual finds himself.

Guardian (2015) opined that the home and environment in which person lives will likely have bearings on his/her academic performance. Education starts from birth to grave and therefore learning can take place anywhere including the homes. The family happens to bear enormous impression on the personality of a child, this personality traits consist of the character and mindset of the child for example high social class children co-exist more than the children of relatively high class parental and this most impressive room for opportunity progressively due to ideology great level of exposure and wealth.

Plourde (2016). Throughout the world, there are students belonging to affluent families that receive distinguished education and students belonging to low in case families that, receive substandard education.

These experiences contribute to the academic achievement gap that has been the source of concern. The income of the parent is the most influential factor for the education of the children. Several researches have explained that the economics status of parents positively influenced the academic performance of the children. Parents of low economic levels are unable to invest sufficiently in the education of their children. Moreover, Aliyis (2016) stated that poor and working class parents prominently focused on the responsibility of providing the basis needs of their children, such as clothing, food and housing.

Aboly-raheem (2015) stated that when families constrained by inadequate resources, children, educational attainment is consequently affected. Furthermore, Aliyu (2016) claimed that parent of low economic status are unable to pay attention to academic activity.

Asiegby and Ezengbor (2018) stated that students of low socio-economic status drop school or parents not interested in sending the children to school because they were unable to pay registration fee, admission fee, PTA fee, exam fee. The cost of the book uniform and transportation from home to school and their daily to school their children to school. Parents of low socio-economic multi-work due to the low remunerable for longer working honours.

Duda (2016) argued that socio-economic status of families as a social and cultural capital that children of poor and working class parents monthly spent their time watering iv, where as high economic class engage in computer, coaching class and tuition. Families of a high economic class are consuming more mobile phones on line games than television. Parents from higher socio-economic backgrounds may also provide higher levels of psychological support for their children through environment that encourage the development of skills necessary for success Ovansa (2017).

In addition, the effect of the background of the family on school achievement is highly prominent in subjects that are deciplinerable to paternal and maternal perceptions. Institutional education encompasses economic price by means of tuition fees, textbooks and other economics, and so many families that is capable of producing these basics is momentarily estimated to get a child all set for school. Some high socio-economic status parents are known to have a library in the human and have the ability to buy

resourceful books for their offspring and even travel than around the world to expand their horizon. In view of Jereh (2015) in all countries, Nigeria inclusive children from poor families most of them lack the economic strength to enroll good school and highly apposite drop out contrast with the children of more stable families. There are certain ways by extreme poverty has been observed to impact on school performance of individual for instance, poverty can make parents unwilling to a child in schools can also make it hard for him to afford books or go on excursions which help to learn better and this further limits the possibility of achieving his/her educational dream goals.

There is no gain saying that the social class differences are likely to affect the academic performance of children. For example parents of different social classes often have difficult child bearing, different ways of communicating expectations and even different ways of reading to their children. These differences do not express themselves consistently or in the case of every family, rather they influence the average tendencies of families from different social classes. It upper-middle class parents have jobs where they are expected to collaborate with fellow employees create new solutions to problem or wonder how to improve their contributions, they are more likely to talk to their children in ways that differ from the ways of lower close parents whose own jobs simply require them to follow instructions without questions.

Parental supports in school setting implies a wide range of behaviours, but conventionally, it refers to parents and family members who invest most of their resources in their children education. These investment are intended to improve the childs learning as such can take place outside the school. Parental support the level of participation that a parent has in the child's education and school. Many parents today are quite involved, often volunteering to help in their children's classroom activities, communicating well with their children's teachers, assisting with their homework and understanding their individual academic strengths and unfortunately, there are so many parents who are not directly involved with their children's education. Parental support at home includes various activities such as helping with homework and reading with children, discussions about school and the like. support at school may include attending workshops, parents voluntarily in the classroom or attending school play and sporting events and above all parental nurturing, family issues, parent education and the like (William, 2011).

Parental support its essential for all children, the nature of parental support changes according to race/ethnicity parents education, economic status of parents and family structure. Today, parents are often faced with unique challenges that hinder them from meeting the academic needs of their children which include time, finance, career or job type. Level of education and time taken to respond to school activities. Insufficient parental support may lead to poor performance of the children academically (Bowen, 2010). A critical appraisal of Obio/Akpor Local Government Area would reveal that it is indeed a class society. In other words, the society differs in social order.

Statement of the Problem

One cannot indeed gain say the fact that social class and parental support play fundamental roles on the academic performance of students. It has equally been observed and established that the success or otherwise of a student is largely determined by the student social class and parental support. Again the backdrop of the above understanding, one can therefore, submit have that barring exceptional cases, students from week to do background tend to do well in schools compared to their counterparts from penurious background. This indeed has an influence on the performance of the students from the opposing/divergent backgrounds. Obio/Akpor Local Government Area is where the several institutions of learning are located, the presence of different parts of the country to come and seek for identify of parents in the lower social class background is that they barely provide all the basic needs to their children education: In otherwords, the motivation (both intimate and extensions) that will bring about academic success is lacking. The government or public school lacks adequate facilities such as textbooks, good classroom building and furniture. Also such schools lack access to the internet. They have poor library in adequate human resources in the form of teadours. Therefore, most of them have to struggle to learn on their own unlike their contemporaries from the elite. For a few of who see the need to study hard to succeed in life, getting submission into the tertiary institution become very difficult.

In the same vein, the highly educated or parents in the higher social class send their children to private schools where everything is provided for the children to learn relevant academic materials such as internet service, textbook and the like are made available. This category of students have good learning environment and are often motivated to learn. A growing operation holds that some of these children from the highly placed homes do not perform well at schools. Some of the reasons that may be advanced includes they are operated, ever pampered, lazy and often not disciplined to study or work hard.

They just want to fulfill the desires of their parents. Their parent are highly placed and have promised than schools abroad or every going to the extent of paying people to write exams for them. They bribe their way into the tertiary institutions. Some of the children also end up as dropouts, others become drug addicting or gang stars thereby becoming nuisance to their families and the society. This research is therefore geared towards examining and unraveling the fundamental relationship between social class and parented support on academic performance of Senior Secondary Schools Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. Specifically, the students sight to:

1. Determine the relationship between social class and parental support on academic achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.
2. Determine the relationship between parent education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.
3. Determine the relationship between parent occupation and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between parent educates and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between parent occupation and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis formulated would guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between parent educational and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.
3. There is no significant between parent occupation and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design which sought to examine relationship between social class and parental support on academic achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The population of the study comprised all students of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. Record available from Rivers State Senior Secondary School Board revealed that there are 112.5 students out of which 4883, one

male and 6352 are female. The sample size of the study was 286 which was determined using Taro Yemen formular distribution. The simple random technique was used to select students of Senior Secondary School Students Class 2 in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The instrument for data collection is questionnaire on social class (QSC) and parental support on academic performance (PCAP), Questionnaire on social class (QSC) and parental support academic performance (PSAD) determined by extent in measurement and evaluation. The experts scrutinized the instrument.

In terms of quality, relevance and appropriateness of the items the internal consistency reliability coefficient of the instruments used for data collection for the study were estimated using Cronbach Alpa method. These liabilities index was 0.78 and 0.82. The instrument was therefore adjudged reliable and suitable enough for the study. A total of 386 instrument was distributed and all the copies were retrieved in good condition and used for the analysis. The data collected for the study were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and co-efficient was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant level.

RESULT

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State?*

Table 1: Relationship between Social class and Parental Support on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

Variable	N	$\frac{Z}{ET}$	$\frac{Z}{ET}$		Remarks		
Social class	(x)	386	1203.10	3904.63			
					4345.95	0.86	High Positive
Parent support on academic (Y)			286	1331.50	5037.15		

The analyses from the table above reveals a correlational on value of $r = 0.56.$, The values is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between social class and parental support academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The relationship have been positive indicates a strong positive relationship exist to social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between parent education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.*

Table 2: Relationship between parent educated and parental support on academic performance Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

Variable	N	$\frac{Zz}{EY}$	$\frac{ZZ}{EY^2}$	Z XZ X	Remarks		
Parental education	(x)	386	455.20	3695.6	4168.95	0.83	High Positive
					4345.95	0.86	High
Parent support on academic of performance (Y)			386	1381.59	5037.1		

From the above table it would be observed that a correlation on coefficient to $r = 0.53$ was obtained upon analysing the relationship between parent education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. A correlation coefficient as high as 0.53 is an indication of a strong relationship between the variables of interest. Moreover, the positive evaluate implies that relationships in the some directions. In his study therefore, the positive correlation value of 0.83 indicates that a strong relationship exists between parent education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between parents occupation and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.*

Table 3:

Variable	N	$\frac{Z}{ET}$	$\frac{Z}{ET}$		Remarks		
Social class	(x)	356	1203.30	3903.5			
				4371.07	4345.95	0.89	High positive
Parent support on academic (Y)		9	386	1381.40	5037.1		

There is positive relationship between parent occupation and parental support on academe performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

This is revealed from the correlations analysis as summarized is the table above, upon analysis of 86 responses on the relationship between parent occupant and parental support on academic performance, a high coefficient value of $r = 0.89$ was attained which obviously background that a positive relationship exist between them.

Hypotheses 1: There is an significant relationship between social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between social and class and parental support on academic performance Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Variable	N	$\frac{Z}{ET}$	$\frac{Z}{ET}$		Remarks			
Social class	(x)	356	1203.30	3903.5				
				4345.98	334	0.05	0.86	0.09
Parent support on academic (Y)		356	1381.59	1381.40	5037.1			
		5						

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between parent education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis of the relationship between parent education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Variable	N	$\frac{Z}{ET}$	$\frac{Z}{ET}$		Remarks			
Social class	(x)	386	1155.2	3696.8				
				4168.5	384	0.05	0.88	0.09
Parent support on academic performance (Y)		386	1381.50	3037.1				
		5						

Table 5 1 showed computation of correlation efficient and t-test value for relationship between peace education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. From the above table, r-calculated of 0.83 is greater than critical value $r = 0.09$ and hence significant and therefore the null hypothesis not accepted. The table also showed the value of computed $t=2917$ and higher compared is the $= 1.96$ at 0.05 level of significance and with f of 389. The confirms that computed valued of r is too significant to be attributed to sampling error and hence the rejection of the null hypotheses is upholds, meaning than is parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant redemption between parent occupation and parental support in academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis of the Relationship between parent occupation and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Variable	N	$\frac{Z}{Z}$	$\frac{Z}{ZY}$	It	Df		Rugi	Tin	Taxi	Remarks
	(x)	386	1203.30	3953.59						
		386	1381.50	5987.1	4371	0.05	0.88	0.09		
Parent support on academic performance (Y)		386	1381.50	3037.1						
		5								

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study in hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between social class and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. Meaning there is high positive relationship between them. The findings of this study is in agreement with the finding of Uwaifo (2018) who found that there is significant relationship between the academic performance of students from rich miles and those from poor families' structure. In line with Ovansa (2017) opined that parents from higher socio-economic background may also provide higher levels of psychological support for their children through environments that encourage the development of skill necessary for successful school.

In support of this view Asiagbu and Ezeugba (2018) assisted that student of low socio-economic status drop the school or parents nor interested in sending fee, PTA, exam fee etc. The finding of this study in hypothesis showed that there is significant high and positive relationship between parent education and parental support on academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

Parents are the most important influence in a child's success in school and in life. Parental support takes many forms including good parenting in the home, including the provision of a secure and stable environment, intellectual stimulation, parent child discussion, good models of constructive social and educational values, and high aspiration relating to personal fulfillment and good citizenship. The income of the parents is the most inflective factor for the education of their children. Parents of low economic levels are unable to invest sufficiently in the educators of their children. Parents of socio-economic engaged in multi work due to the low remuneration for longer working hours. Parents from higher socio-economic background may provide higher level of psychological support for their children through environment that encourage development of skills necessary for success at school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Government, multi-national companies and public sprinted individual should be able to identify and support intelligent students from low – income parents with view to boosting their academic performance.
2. Parents should try to improve as much as possible in their level of educator became it has significant influence on their children academic performance in Senior Secondary Schools.
3. Parents should try as must as possible not to sacrifice the academic well-being of their children on the altar of their jobs.

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